

Management

A NOVEL TOURISM COMPETITIVENESS RANK

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Abstract

This paper proposes a novel tourism rank to arrange countries in tourism. The proposed rank is based on fifteen factors, the fourteen factors affecting the tourism rank considered in the Travel & Tourism competitiveness reports and the number of tourist arrivals considered in United Nations World Tourism Organization rank. The proposed method gives significant differences compared to the traditional ranks used by the Travel & Tourism competitiveness reports and United Nations World Tourism Organization rank.

Keywords: Travel and Tourism Competitiveness; Tourism Country Rank; Proposed Rank; United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

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1. Introduction

Tourism is an important factor to the economy of all countries. The Tourism rank of any country reflects its attractiveness to tourist arrivals. There are two well-known tourism ranks, the first one of The United Nations World Tourism Organization and is based on the number of tourist arrivals, the other due to Travel & Tourism competitiveness report and is based on 14 factors listed in International Travel and Tourism reports [1] and these factors divided into 3 main groups as follows:

Group 1

Travel & Tourism regulatory framework and includes 5 factors

- 1) Policy rules and regulations.
- 2) Environmental sustainability.
- 3) Safety and security.

- 4) Health and hygiene.
- 5) Prioritization of Travel & Tourism.

Group 2

Travel & Tourism business environment and infrastructure and includes 5 factors

- 6) Air transport infrastructure.
- 7) Ground transport infrastructure.
- 8) Tourism infrastructure.
- 9) ICT infrastructure.
- 10) Price competitiveness in the T&T industry.

Group 3

Travel & Tourism human, cultural, and natural resources and includes 4 factors

- 11) Human resources.
- 12) Affinity for Travel & Tourism.
- 13) Natural resources.
- 14) Cultural resources.

The UNWTO tourism rank is the ranking of countries according to the number of tourist arrivals (the country with the highest number of tourist arrivals has rank 1 and so on). Table (1) shows the number of tourist arrivals and the country rank during (2008 – 2013) in United Nations World Tourism Organization.

Table 1: Country rank of United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO)

Country	2008		2009		2011		2013	
	International Tourist arrivals (million)	Rank						
France	79.2	1	76.8	1	81.6	1	83.6	1
United States	57.9	2	55.0	2	62.7	2	70.0	2
Spain	57.2	3	52.2	3	56.2	4	60.7	3
China	53.0	4	50.9	4	57.6	3	55.7	4
Italy	42.7	5	43.2	5	46.1	5	47.7	5
United Kingdom	30.1	6	28.2	6	29.3	7	31.1	8
Turkey	25.0	7	25.5	7	34.7	6	37.8	6
Germany	24.9	8	24.2	8	28.4	8	31.5	7
Malaysia	22.1	10	23.6	9	24.7	9	Out	Out
Mexico	22.6	9	21.5	10	Out	Out	24.2	10
Russian Federation	Out	Out	Out	Out	22.7	10	28.4	9

Source: United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), UNWTO Tourism Highlights 2010, 2011, 2013 and 2015 Editions [5], [6], [7] and [8].

Another international ranking is given by Travel & Tourism Competitiveness report. Each country has a score calculated as given in the Travel & Tourism Competitiveness report. The country with the highest score has rank 1 and so on. Table (2) shows the score and country rank in the travel & tourism competitiveness reports. The mentioned ranks are not the same.

Table 2: Score and country rank in the Travel & Tourism Competitiveness reports

Country	2008		2009		2011		2013	
	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score
Switzerland	1	5.63	1	5.68	1	5.68	1	5.66
Germany	2	5.41	2	5.41	2	5.50	2	5.39
Spain	3	5.30	4	5.29	6	5.29	3	5.38
United Kingdom	4	5.28	6	5.22	5	5.30	4	5.38
United States	5	5.28	5	5.28	4	5.30	5	5.32
France	6	5.23	3	5.34	3	5.41	6	5.31
Italy	7	4.84	7	4.78	7	4.87	7	4.90
Malaysia	8	4.63	8	4.71	8	4.59	8	4.70
Turkey	9	4.19	11	4.20	11	4.37	11	4.44
Mexico	10	4.18	10	4.29	10	4.43	9	4.46
China	11	4.06	9	4.33	9	4.47	10	4.45
Russian Federation	12	4.04	12	4.14	12	4.23	12	4.16
Egypt	13	3.96	13	4.09	13	3.96	14	3.88
Ukraine	14	3.76	14	3.84	14	3.83	13	3.98

Source: The Travel and Tourism competitiveness report 2008, 2009, 2011 and 2013 reports [1], [2], [3] and [4].

2. The Proposed Rank

The proposed rank is based on 15 factors, the number of tourist arrivals in addition to the 14 factors considered in the Travel & the Tourism competitiveness report. The proposed rank can be calculated for any year using the following steps:.

1-For a given country, i and factor j , calculate the standard value of factor j (a value in the interval $[1, 2]$) $T_i(j)$ of the factor j , where

$$T_i(j) = \frac{\text{existing score}(j) - \min(j)}{\text{Max}(j) - \min(j)} + 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, 15$$

Where;

$\text{Max}(j)$ and $\text{Min}(j)$ are the maximum and minimum score of the factor j for the given country(i) in T&T competitiveness reports.

2- For any country i , $i=1,2,\dots,14$ Find the country score $T_{i \text{ total}}(i)$, where

$$T_{i \text{ total}}(i) = \left[\prod_{j=1}^{15} T_i(j) \right]$$

3- Order The $T_{i \text{ total}}$, $i=1, 2, \dots, 14$ values from highest to lowest and give the highest value of $T_{i \text{ total}}$ the order 1 and so on.

The following tables give comparisons between the proposed rank and the other ranks in 2008, 2009, 2011, and 2013.

Table 3: Comparison between the proposed rank and other ranks in 2008

Country	Proposed rank	Rank in travel and tourism report	Rank in UNWTO
Switzerland	Out	1	Out
Germany	3	2	8
United Kingdom	5	4	6
France	1	6	1
Spain	2	3	3
United States	4	5	2
Malaysia	6	8	10
Italy	7	7	5
Turkey	8	9	7
Mexico	9	10	9
Egypt	Out	13	Out
China	10	11	4
Russian Federation	Out	12	Out
Ukraine	Out	14	Out

Table 4: Comparison between proposed rank and other ranks in 2009

Country	Proposed rank	Rank in travel & tourism report	Rank in UNWTO
Switzerland	Out	1	Out
Germany	3	2	8
United Kingdom	5	6	6
France	1	3	1
Spain	2	4	3
United States	4	5	2
Malaysia	6	8	9
Italy	7	7	5
Turkey	9	11	7
Mexico	10	10	10
Egypt	Out	13	Out
China	8	9	4
Russian Federation	Out	12	Out
Ukraine	Out	14	Out

Table 5: Comparison between proposed rank and other ranks in 2011

Country	Proposed rank	Rank in travel & tourism report	Rank in UNWTO
Switzerland	Out	1	Out
Germany	2	2	8
United Kingdom	5	5	7
France	1	3	1

Spain	3	6	4
United States	4	4	2
Malaysia	7	8	9
Italy	6	7	5
Turkey	9	11	6
Mexico	Out	10	Out
Egypt	Out	13	Out
China	8	9	3
Russian Federation	10	12	10
Ukraine	Out	14	Out

Table 6: Comparison between proposed rank and other ranks in 2013

Country	Proposed rank	Rank in travel & tourism report	Rank in UNWTO
Switzerland	Out	1	Out
Germany	5	2	7
United Kingdom	3	4	8
France	1	6	1
Spain	2	3	3
United States	4	5	2
Malaysia	Out	8	Out
Italy	6	7	5
Turkey	7	11	6
Mexico	9	9	10
Egypt	Out	14	Out
China	8	10	4
Russian Federation	10	12	9
Ukraine	Out	13	Out

3. Discussion and Conclusion

- 1) The proposed rank takes into consideration fifteen factors affecting the tourism in any country and is easily calculated.
- 2) The given rank is more realistic than the other used methods hence the other two international ranks are special cases of the proposed one.
- 3) There are a significant difference between the proposed rank and the other two international ranks of United Nations World Tourism Organization and Travel & Tourism Competitiveness reports.
- 4) The given idea deserves to be considered by the international tourism organizations.

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